

Work-Life Balance Among Women School Teachers (Aided)

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“Nobody can go back and start a new beginning,

But anyone can start today and make a new ending”

- Maria Robinson

Abstract

Work-life balance has become a vital concern for both research scholars, employees and the employer in present time, to find out academic reasons and attempt to provide a holistic picture of work-life balance and programmes (WLBP) offered by various institutions in India, Having the basis of extant literature, primary and secondary data. This paper has made an attempt to understand the current status of WLBP in Indian institutions of Aided schools, to notify its future prospects. The paper is discussing the challenges for effective implementation of new thoughts and ideas, which can help institution heads to be cautious before introducing WLBP in their respective institutions. Analysis of literature and available data suggests that family-friendliness of teachers in India and has been reflected in various welfare provisions which has been a matter of concern for teachers. With time, the scope and coverage of such initiatives have broadened and have become more individual growth and family well-being oriented. However, the range of WLBP varies across the institutions and there is still a long way to go.

Keywords: Stress Management, Work-Family Balance, (WFB) Work-Life Balance, (WLB) Work Place Stress, Personal Life, Professional Life, Work pressures, Regulations and Technological Advancement.

Introduction

The social, political and economical fabric of societies Changes have influenced and continue to influence both the nature of employment and its relationship to life outside work.

Work-life balance has emerged as a hot topic in recent times—fuelled in part by changing trends in women’s social roles. Changing employment patterns together with changes in the demographic structure of the work field have resulted in a different reality for the 21st century. Instead of trying to manage lots of leisure time, many teachers are instead trying to juggle numerous responsibilities with the increased, intensified demands of work. In particular, transformations in the structure of both the workplace and the workforce imply that

work practices and employers' expectations must change accordingly. "Every role has its own exception". The traditional assumption that employees should be willing and able to make work their top

Priority in life is no longer justifiable. Globalization, new technologies are challenging the long sustainable patterns of paid work while imposing new burdens on families, individuals and households. Until quite recently it was widely assumed, particularly in and concerning the richer countries, that working hours were steadily reducing, the amount of leisure time increasing and that these trends would continue.

Work Life-Life Balance: Conceptual Overview

The American Society of Training and Development (ASTD) defined the concept of Work-Life Balance (WLB) as the degree to which members of an organization are able to satisfy their personal needs through their experiences in the organizations. It focuses on creating a human work environment where employees work cooperatively and add to organizational objectives (Chhabra, 2010). Byrne (2005) describes work life balance as juggling of five aspects of one's life at any one point in time: work, family, friends, health and self. Clutterback (2003) defined work-life balance as awareness of different demands in relation to energy and time, ability to allocate the time and energy among different domains of work and life and then to apply and make choice.

Sparrow and Cooper (2003) suggested that work-life balance include those practices that have the capacity to increase the autonomy and flexibility of employees in the process of balancing different requirements. There are work-life balance issues that are extremely important in the workplace, these are: increased level of stress, competitions and insecurities in the workplace. All these factors are important and they lead to disruption in work-life balance (Bonney, 2005). Though it is not easy for any organization to incorporate all the employee friendly policies, but such types of policies are beneficial for employee, employers as well as the society at large. These benefits include lower absenteeism, increased productivity, reduced overheads, improved recruitment and retention, satisfied and equitable workforce and improved customer experience (Aityan, 2011; Budd & Mumford, 2005). Family-friendly work environment such as flexi time, work from home and job sharing has been portrayed as an important component of an employee's preferences towards work time. It has been suggested that such types of work arrangement help employees' in obtaining a better balance between their work and personal lives while providing organizations with a means of recruiting, retaining and motivating their work force (Bachmann, 2000; Schwartz, 1994). It has been found that lack of balance between work and personal activities is related to reduce physical and psychological well-being (Frone et al., 1997; Martens et al., 1999; Sparks et al., 1997). Hyman et al. (2003) indicated that intrusion of work demands into personal life (e.g. working during the week-end) was related with reports of increased stress and emotional exhaustion for employees. Furthermore, employees perceived that intrusion of work obligations into their personal lives negatively affected their health. Work-life balance is about effectively managing the juggling act between paid work and all other activities that are important to people such as family, social activities, voluntary work, personal development, leisure and recreation (Dundas, 2008). Work life balance is based on the assumption of the separation of work from the private life and that 'balance' is achieved when there is equal division between the two (Khallash & Kruse, 2012). Employers are interested in satisfying demands related to employee work-life balance because of expected positive outcomes like job satisfaction, organizational commitment, loyalty and retention (Forsyth & Polzer-Debruyne, 2007).

The number of women working as teachers in different schools is great. Most of them belong to the group of dual career couples. These teachers have a dual commitment to fulfill. They have to be committed to their work and at the same time they have their commitment to their homes,

spouses, children, relatives and friends. Their involvement in their work infringes on their personal life and if they also find their personal life affects their work. There are a number of factors in the work that cause stress to the teachers. Pupil-teacher ratio, rigid education system and school organization, unstable educational policy and fragmentation of responsibilities, absence of reward for quality work, poor guidance, unfavourable condition for team work, too little time for out of school activities, increased workload owing to proliferation of subjects added responsibilities without increase in resources, loss of job satisfaction and low morale are the major causes that produce stress for the teachers in their work place. Work and commitment to work can either enhance or depreciate family life. Similarly, family life can produce either positive or negative influence on work attitude, behaviour and outcome. Extensive and inflexible working hours lead to job stress, which in turn produces distress within the family domain, withdrawal from family responsibilities, adversely affecting the overall quality of a teacher's life. Women teachers feel that they must do justice to their work. But at the same time they have to take care of their families also. Such a situation results in additional stress.

At this juncture the study of work life balance among the women school teachers will help to predict how they will react towards certain stressful situation. As a teacher, the researcher want to identify the problem of women teachers working at different level of institution in relation to certain selected variables, which seems to be the need of the hour. A clear link is perceived in all contexts between the status of teachers and their working conditions and living conditions. Hence there is an absolute need for the study of work life balance among women school teachers. Variables such as ability in handling different attitude towards their work and to help improve their situations in their field such as satisfaction from work, attitude to work and colleagues and attitude towards family and family members are selected for the present study.

Review of Literature

Campbell (1993) studied the effects of family life on women's job performance and work attitudes. The result revealed that women with children were significantly lower in occupational commitment relative to women without children; contrary to expectation, women with younger children outperformed women with older children.

Brown. J.R, (1996) he identified the three major reasons (all intrinsic) as to why teachers leave the profession are; the need for personal growth, the desire for a philosophy of education, and lack of respect and recognition of their efforts.

Ingersoll.R.M, (1997) maintains that teacher professionalism the movement to upgrade the status, training and working conditions of teachers – has received a great deal of interest ever since.

Tim Hindle (1998) has said that the effects of stress are closely linked to individual personality. The same level of stress affects different people in different ways and each person has different coping strategies for coping stress can be divided into two main categories- adoptive and maladaptive. The former tends to lead towards the problems being resolved, while the latter can increase problems. Further, he said finding a balanced life style and a self-assessment exercise are essential to overall wellbeing.

Marta Elliott, (2003) conducted a study on “work and family role strain among university employees” with data from a survey of faculty and staff of a public university in the western U.S. The results indicated that difficulties in taking care of children and elderly dependents are the primary causes of work and family role strain in the family domain, while dissatisfaction with resources and perceived unfair criticism are primary in the work domain. The predictors of work and family role strain are similar for faculty and staff, for both men and women, with one exception: Having a supportive spouse or partner reduces work and family role strain to a great extent for women than it does for men.

Karakas and lee, (2004) explained work life balance issues as spending good time with family members, getting free time to be able to relax for emotional well being and health of family members, having good communication and support from fellow colleagues, obtaining high quality child care and education; and being satisfied with the work load.

Rao S.S and Aiswarya Ramasundaram (2009) in their study had tried to bring out the relationship and the effect of the demographic profile on the levels of depression. The empirical study was undertaken on academic women employees. Statistical analysis proves that depression exists among all women employees across the demographic characters namely age groups, number of children, educational background, and number of dependants with significant differences. The authors concluded that interventions to lessen employees' work – family conflict may reduce depression. The study also highlighted that the organization has to reframe policies and programs, to assist employees to manage the tasks that 'work' and 'family' demands.

Rupashree and Shivganesh (2010) in their study, reported that supervisor support and work-family culture are positively related to job satisfaction and commitment. No significant association was found between Work-Life Benefits and Policies (WLBP) and job outcome measures. Job characteristics and supervisor support were positively related to work family enrichment. Work family enrichment mediated the relationships between job characteristics and job outcomes and between supervisor support and affective commitment.

Makowska (2010) studied psychosocial determinants of stress and well-being among working women. The significance of the work-related stressors was evidently greater than that of the stressors associated with the family function, although the relationship between family functioning, stress and well-being was also significant.

Sharafizad, Fleur; Paull, Megan; Omari, Maryam (2011) made a study on "Flexible Work arrangements and accessibility in a University Environment. The findings indicate that employee job type is significantly related to the take up of flexible work arrangements as well as employee satisfaction with current work-life balance. Academic staff appear to have limited ability to access flexible work arrangements due to their increasing workload, and were significantly less satisfied with their current work-life balance than their general staff colleagues. There are implications arising from this research for all stakeholder groups.

Bridges, Sue; Searle, Annette (2011) in their study found Changing Workloads of Primary School Teachers: "I Seem to live on the Edge of Chaos". The roles and workloads of teachers have been widely noted as changing considerably over recent decades. In this 2009 replication of a 1992 study, 379 New Zealand primary school educators were surveyed regarding their workloads, how these changed, as well as their perceived sustainability. It investigates how respondents believe that educational reforms and initiatives impact on their work, their home life, their health, and their view of teaching as a career. Results from both cohorts signal warnings to school leaders as workloads increase in hours and complexity, leaving educators to grapple with the complicated balance of demands made of them.

A.K.M.Mominul Haque Talukder (2011) studied work life balance in service context and made attempts to identify how employees are balancing their work life by considering variables such as work culture, job satisfaction, employee benefits, work environment, flexible work time, work load and discrimination. He identified that work life balance is influenced by all these variables.

Santha Lakshmi.K & Dr.N.Santhosh Kumar (2011) studied 250 women employees at SRM University and found that working women undergo severe stress as they try to balance their domestic life and professional life. They revealed that continued work under pressure would result in poor performance at the institution as well as domestic life.

Definitions of Work-Life Balance

An in depth analysis of the views of economists on work-life balance is indeed necessary to understand how work-life balance has enhanced economic development. Sparrow and Cooper (2003) observe that “Work-life balance concerns those practices that enhance the flexibility and autonomy of the employee in this process of integration and in the negotiation over the attention and presence required”. Bratton and Gold (2003) give a broader definition of work – life balance, as the need to “balance work and leisure family activities”. Electwood (2007) goes further in suggesting that Work-life balance is about “People having a measure of control over when, where and how they work”.

Work family balance is generally thought to promote well-being, Kofodimos (1993) suggests that imbalance-in particular work imbalance -arouses high levels of stress, detracts from quality of life, and ultimately reduces individuals effectiveness at work. Hall (1990) proposes an organizational change of approach to promising work family balance, and the popular press is replicate with advice to companies and employees on how to promote greater balance in life. Cummings,(2001);Fisher,(2001) IZZ and Withers, (2001) define work-life balance as “Working practices that acknowledge and aim to support the needs of staff in achieving a balance between their home and working lives”.

Importance of Work Life Balance to Women

Today’s career women are continually challenged by the demands of full-time work and when the day is done at the office, they carry more of the responsibilities and commitments at home. When survey is conducted (Osmania University, Hyderabad), discovered that the majority of women are working 4045 hours per week and 53% of the respondents report that they are struggling to achieve work/life balance.

Women report that their lives are a juggling act that includes multiple responsibilities at work, heavy meeting schedules, business trips, on top of managing the daily routine responsibilities of life and home. “Successfully achieving work/life balance will ultimately create a more satisfied workforce that contributes to productivity and success in the workplace.”

Need for Research

The area of work-life balance has been receiving significant research attention in recent times. There are several reasons that highlight the need for research in this area:

Due to high level of stress and increasing competition, more emphasis is laid on implementing work-life balance program in organizations (Bonney, 2005). Expansion in the workplace (i.e. both national and international) and in employee demographics (more women in workplace) in the past decade has led to an increased anxiety over the creation of proper boundary between employee work and personal lives. Thus, WLB can be used as a key component in any organization as employee retention strategy (Nord et al., 2002). An empirical examination of work-life balance scenario is thus, essential to understand this domain of knowledge.

An extensive literature review in the field of work-life balance and organization commitment reveals that there are very few studies in the Indian context incorporating both the dimensions. Thus, it was felt that there is a need to study the relationships between the two important areas.

Studies have been carried out quite extensively on work-life balance issues in the context of the corporate world. However, there is a lack of such studies in the field of academics. Borg and Riding (1991) concluded that teaching is stressful. It has been found that between 5% and 20% of all teachers are burned out at any given time (Farber, 1991). In a study it was found that educators have the highest level of WLB problems in comparison to other white collar jobs (Kalimo &

Hakanen, 2000). There is thus, a need for research in the context of academicians. The extant studies on academics are mainly in the Western world. Thus, the area remains largely unexplored in the context of academicians in India.

Further, most studies on teachers in the area of work-life balance have focused on higher education teachers. Teachers in the school education institutions in India have not been covered in these studies. There is lack of researches in the areas on teachers in school education in the Indian context. Thus, this present study is expected to fill the gap.

The present study attempts to bridge the methodological gap that was left unattended in the previous researches. In the present research, quantitative data analysis is supplemented with qualitative analysis in order to provide more meaningful results as suggested by researchers (Boyatzis, 1998; Roulston, 2001). Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was deployed as it has the ability to take into account measurement error by estimating measurement error variances from the data and model specification, whereas traditional techniques do not (Ahire et al., 1996). The present research also takes into consideration a fairly large sample size as compared to previous researches, thereby filling the gap in terms of small sample related problems.

It is an accepted truth that highly qualified and satisfied teaching staff is the cornerstone of a successful society. It has been realized that a good teacher is a primary requirement for establishing a successful educational institution (Sharma & Jyoti, 2006). The most severe consequence of a dissatisfied teacher in its negative effect on teaching quality and student achievement (Geringer, 2000). Thus, work-life balance of teachers is a critical area that needs to be addressed in order to enhance teachers' satisfactions and retention. Thus, a study in the area will help meet the societal goal of identifying strategies to help teachers balance work-life aspects in order to enhance overall quality of education in the country.

Objectives of Study

Based on the review of literature, the objectives of the study are:

1. To study the demographic characteristics of the women school teachers.
2. To find out job satisfaction among the women school teachers.
3. To identify the job stress among the women school teachers.
4. To assess the attitude towards teaching profession among the school teachers.
5. To examine the organizational climate of the schools in the study area.
6. To analyze the important antecedents of work life balance among the school teachers.
7. To measure the work life balance among the women school teachers.
8. To analyze the level of implementation of coping strategies and its impact on the work life balance among the women school teachers.
9. To suggest the suitable measures for policy making to improve the job satisfaction, organizational climate and work life balance among the school teachers.

Work-Life Balance of Women Teachers

Key Strengths of Indian Women Teachers as Heads

- Ability to network with colleagues
- Ability to perceive and understand situations
- Strong sense of dedication, loyalty and commitment to their institutions
- Ability to multitask
- Collaborative work style-solicit input from others, with respect for ideas
- Crisis management skills
- Willingness to share information (interactive leadership style)
- Sensitivity in relationships (e.g., compassionate, empathetic, understanding)
- Behaving in a gender-neutral manner.

Recommended Practices to Create a “Women Teachers-Friendly” Institutions

- Senior management commitment to gender issues.
- Career development programs for women.
- Exposure of women to top levels.
- Leadership development programs for women teachers.
- Job rotation for women teachers.
- Recruitment of women teachers at senior-level positions.
- Regular survey of women teachers to assess job satisfaction.
- Mentoring programs for women teachers.

Recommendations for Aided Institutions

- Indian society broadly supports Indian women in managerial positions, organizations need to be more open and make appropriate changes in their workplace. From the Indian research study *Women in Management in the New Economic Environment: the Case of India*, the following are recommendations for Indian organizations to promote a supportive workplace for women.
- Establish training programs for women teachers, such as mentorships, career guidance and leadership development.
- Promote awareness initiatives that highlight the value of women teachers.
- Elicit input from women teachers regarding policies, promotion and performance review processes of students and the managements.
- Make accommodations for women teachers in areas such as need-based postings. That is, as done in civil services, have a policy to post both spouses to the same district or state.
- Have a true commitment to hire and promote women teachers and include women teachers in the annual meetings for the promotion of students and teaching strategy.

Conclusion

Work/life programs have the potential to significantly improve women teachers morale, and reduce absenteeism for routine duties. And also retains professional knowledge, particularly during difficult time of teaching and promoting strength. In today’s global, privatization situation, the schools aim to reduce costs of fees and tries to upgrade the bench mark in academic curriculum and it falls to the human resource professional to understand the critical issues of work/life balance and champion work/life programs. Work life balance programmes create win – win situation for institutions as well as women teachers.

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